

Physiological Changes in Women's Sleep Across their Lifespan

Ana Teresa Lima, MD*, Maria José Guimarães¹, MD, Mariana Antunes¹, Maria Gomes¹

1. Dr Maria José Guimarães Sleep Clinic, Portugal

Correspondence to: Ana Teresa Lima, MD, .

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Abstract

Objective: Assess the effect of ageing on women's sleep.

Methods: We analysed the reports of polysomnographic studies from a sleep clinic, performed in adult women from all ages.

Results: NREM sleep correlated positively with age and REM sleep correlated inversely with age, both with a statistically moderate association. WASO (Wakefulness After Sleep Onset), REM latency, ODI (Oxygen Desaturation Index) and snore correlated positively with age, with a statistically weak association. Sleep efficiency showed a weak negative correlation with ageing. Comparing two groups of women, below and above 50 years old, only REM latency, AHI (Apnea-Hypopnea Index), ODI and snore(%) showed statistically significant differences, with older women presenting higher values in all of these parameters.

Conclusion: Our study demonstrated an overall poorer sleep in women with increasing age. However, we still need more studies that clarify the exact mechanisms behind these gender and age differences in sleep, so that we know how to manage problems properly and improve women's quality of life.

Keywords: Ageing; Polysomnography; REM sleep; Sleep efficiency; WASO; Women.

Introduction

Sleep is unquestionably crucial for health and well-being. Disrupted sleep negatively impacts cognition, impairs memory consolidation, weakens the immune system and increases the risk of numerous diseases and indicators of health, such as obesity, cardiovascular disease, Alzheimer's disease and psychiatric disorders. [1] Particularly, REM (rapid eye movement) sleep deprivation is associated with enhanced emotional reactivity, adverse health outcomes and higher mortality. [2]

However, there is a clear gender bias in reported sleep difficulties and disorders, with significant implications for women's quality of life. Women usually report poorer sleep than men and have more sleep complaints.

They are more likely to report longer sleep latency, more nocturnal awakenings, as well as more daytime sleepiness. Women are 41% more likely to experience insomnia than men, and this risk increases with age, and are also more than twice as likely to suffer from anxiety and depressive disorders, which are known causes of sleep disturbance. They also have twice the risk of experiencing restless legs syndrome (RLS). [1] Most patients with RLS also experience periodic limb movements of sleep (PLMS). The prevalence of PLMS increases with age and is also more prevalent in women. [3]

Therefore, to improve women's health across their lifespan, it is crucial to understand if sleep objectively changes and how it changes during the different phases of a woman's life. Additionally, more studies are needed to clearly identify the biological sources behind gender differences in sleep and, consequently, determine potential substrates accessible to clinical intervention. Many studies point out the role of ovarian hormones in mediating these gender differences in sleep and acutely regulating and influencing various parameters of women's sleep. [4, 5, 6, 7]

REM sleep seems to be modulated during the menstrual cycle and premenstrual syndrome (PMS) may disrupt sleep severely. [8]

Pregnancy is also associated with sleep modulations. [8, 9]

Problems with sleep are also very common during menopause, particularly associated with vasomotor symptoms, and alleviating these symptoms improves perceived sleep quality. In premenopause, sleep-disordered breathing (SDB), including obstructive sleep apnea (OSA), is more common in men than women. However, women run the risk of being underdiagnosed for the disease, as they frequently present atypical symptoms, which may develop with a lower apnea-hypopnea index (AHI). [8]

In pregnancy, sleep disturbance may not be related to changes in ovarian hormones but rather to physiological factors, such as differences in sleeping position, increase in nocturnal micturition, gastroesophageal reflux or musculoskeletal discomfort, factors that possibly mask any effect of hormones. [2]

Nonetheless, estrogen, both endogenous and exogenous, as well as progesterone, are positively associated with sleep quality during the menopausal transition. Menopausal hormone therapy (MHT) improves sleep disturbances that characterize this period. [2]

However, ageing itself is related to a decrease in sleep quality and quantity for both men and women. [10] In fact, for women, both ageing and hormonal changes independently influence sleep architecture. Ageing is associated with decreased total sleep time (TST), more awakenings during the night and poorer sleep efficiency, regardless of menopausal state. [11]

Sleep disturbances increase with advancing age, affecting nearly half of the individuals with more than 65 years old, especially the female population, with a negative impact on women's physical and emotional well-being. [2]

Therefore, the purpose of this investigation is to assess the effect of ageing on female's sleep in our sample of Portuguese women. Understanding sleep changes across the lifespan is important to distinguish clinical sleep conditions or complaints as physiological or pathological and may ultimately lead to effective therapies that improve health and well-being for women, who were, until very recently, excluded from sleep studies.

Methods

This was an observational, analytical and retrospective study conducted in a differentiated Sleep Clinic. We included adult women of all ages who performed polysomnographic studies level I (in the sleep laboratory) and level II (in ambulatory) as well as level III with the artificial intelligence algorithm BodySleep® in the Clinic, between May 2022 and June 2024.

The following parameters were collected: age; BMI (Body Mass Index); TRT (Total Recording Time), the time from lights off to lights on; TST (Total Sleep Time), the time spent asleep while in bed; sleep efficiency, defined as the percentage of sleep during time spent in bed; WASO (Wakefulness After Sleep Onset), meaning the total number of minutes that a person is awake after having initially fallen asleep; sleep latency, the time from lights out to the first epoch of any stage of sleep; REM latency, the time between sleep onset and the first epoch of REM sleep; AHI (Apnea-Hypopnea Index), the combined average number of apneas and hypopneas that occur per hour of sleep; ODI (Oxygen Desaturation Index), the average number of desaturation episodes occurring per hour, where desaturation is defined as a decrease in the mean oxygen saturation of $\geq 3\%$ for a minimum of 3 seconds; percentage of snore; PLMS (Periodic Limb Movements of Sleep) index; percentage of REM sleep; percentage of NREM sleep, the sum of the percentages of all stages of NREM – N1, N2 and N3; arousal index in TST, which indicates the number of times a person wakes up per hour of sleep; average pulse, maximum pulse and minimum pulse in TST.

Ethical considerations

The patients' anonymity and confidentiality were guaranteed. The study took place in accordance with ethical principles and good practice.

The research protocol was submitted and approved by the Ethics Committee for Research in Life and Health Sciences (CEICVS) of the Ethics Council of University of Minho.

Statistical analysis

The analyses were performed using IBM SPSS software (version 29) and the level of significance adopted was 0.05.

Normality of data was checked by Shapiro-Wilk tests. Quantitative data conforming to a normal distribution were represented as mean \pm standard deviation. Non-normally distributed data were presented as medians (P25; P75). Count data were expressed in percentages (%). All results were presented using suitable statistics for qualitative and quantitative variables, using the Chi-square test and Student's t-test or Mann-Whitney U test, respectively.

The existence of a correlation between age and sleep parameters was assessed by computing the corresponding Pearson (R) or Spearman (rho) coefficient, according to the normality test. The strength of the relationship was defined as weak with a correlation coefficient of [0.2, 0.4[or moderate if coefficient of [0.4, 0.6[.

Missing values in the measure were discarded and not considered for the calculations.

The effect size of statistically significant results was calculated using SPSS and Excel. For parametric tests, the effect size was measured by Cohen's d, and the convention for a small (0.2 - 0.5), medium (0.5 - 0.8) and large (≥ 0.8) effect size was based on Cohen's (1988) approach. [12] While for non-parametric tests, the effect size r was calculated as Z statistic divided by square root of the sample size (N) (Z/\sqrt{N}). The interpretation values used for r were the following: 0.1 - <0.3 (small effect), 0.3 - <0.5 (moderate effect) and ≥ 0.5 (large effect). [13]

Results

Construction of Study Sample

The study sample is constituted by 60 women. The overall sample ranges in age from 25 to 83 years, with a mean age of 50.4 years.

Sleep efficiency is used as an exclusion criterion. Cases with sleep efficiency below 80% were excluded, in order to rule out cases of insomnia and to ensure we only included women who have slept objectively well.

Table 1 summarizes the demographic and sleep efficiency characterization of the patients in the whole sample.

Variables	Initial sample (N=60)
<i>Age (years)</i>	
Sample size (N subjects)	60
Mean ± SD	50.4 ± 14.7
Range	25 - 83
<i>BMI (Kg/m²)</i>	
Sample size (N)	59
Median (P25; P75)	24.3 (22.0; 27.4)
Range	18.7 - 44.9
Normal weight N(%)	35 (59.3%)
Overweight N(%)	17 (28.8%)
Obesity N(%)	7 (11.9%)
<i>Sleep efficiency (%)</i>	
Sample size (N)	60
< 80% (N)	19
≥ 80% (N)	41
Median (P25; P75)	86.5 (74.8; 91.6)
Range	35.8 - 96.7

Table 1. Demographic and sleep efficiency characteristics of the total study sample

So, a total of 41 women with sleep efficiency higher than 80% were included in this study, spanning an age range from 26 to 82 years. Next, we categorized our sample into two age groups: group 1, with age below 50 years (Young adults: 26-49 years, n = 28) and group 2, with women aged 50 and over (Adults: 51-82 years, n = 13).

The socio-demographic characteristics of the two age groups are listed in Table 2.

Socio-demographic characteristics	Full sample	Age < 50 years	Age ≥ 50 years	p-value
<i>Age (years)</i>				
Sample size (N subjects)	41 (100%)	28 (68.3%)	13 (31.7%)	
Mean ± SD	47.8 ± 13.2	40.6 ± 6.4	63.3 ± 10.4	<0.001
Range	26 - 82	26 - 49	51 - 82	
<i>Gender</i>				
Female (N)	41 (100%)	28 (68.3%)	13 (31.7%)	
<i>BMI (Kg/m²)</i>				
Sample size N(%)	40 (100%)	28 (70.0%)	12 (30.0%)	
Median (P25; P75)	24.3 (21.5; 27.4)	23.6 (20.7; 27.4)	25.9 (22.7; 27.7)	0.209
Range	18.7 - 44.9	18.7 - 44.9	21.1 - 32.8	
Normal weight N(%)	23 (57.5%)	18 (64.3%)	5 (41.7%)	0.185
Overweight N(%)	13 (32.5%)	7 (25.0%)	6 (50.0%)	0.122
Obesity N(%)	4 (10.0%)	3 (10.7%)	1 (8.3%)	1.000

Table 2. Socio-demographic characteristics.

Table 3 summarizes the sleep characterization of the female sample (N = 41).

Sleep Characteristics	Full sample	Age < 50 years	Age ≥ 50 years	p-value
<i>TRT (Total Recording Time) (min)</i>				
Sample size (N)	41 (100%)	28 (68.3%)	13 (31.7%)	0.639
Mean ± SD	520.3 ± 61.0	523.4 ± 65.4	513.6 ± 50.8	
Median (P25; P75)	512 (478; 550)	512 (483; 559)	520 (478; 550)	
Range	393 - 682	393 - 682	429 - 595	
<i>TST (Total Sleep Time) (min)</i>				
Sample size (N)	41 (100%)	28 (68.3%)	13 (31.7%)	0.220
Mean ± SD	464.3 ± 59	472.0 ± 62.6	447.7 ± 47.0	
Median (P25; P75)	455 (428; 502)	457.5 (431; 520.0)	448 (419; 474)	
Range	340 - 608	340 - 608	367 - 529	
<i>Sleep efficiency (%)</i>				
Sample size (N)	41 (100%)	28 (68.3%)	13 (31.7%)	0.081
Mean ± SD	89.2 ± 4.8	90.1 ± 4.1	87.3 ± 5.7	
Median (P25; P75)	90.1 (86.5; 93.2)	90.7 (86.95; 93.4)	88.6 (80.7; 91.5)	
Range	80.3 - 96.7	81.2 - 96.7	80.3 - 96.1	

<i>WASO (Wakefulness After</i>				
<i>Sleep Onset) (min)</i>				
Sample size (N)	41 (100%)	28 (68.3%)	13 (31.7%)	
Mean ± SD	35.5 ± 17.7	32.6 ± 16.7	41.7 ± 18.7	0.123
Median (P25; P75)	32.5 (23; 41.8)	30.9 (19.3; 39.9)	35 (28.0; 57.1)	
Range	7.5 - 77.6	7.5 - 75.7	21.0 - 77.6	
<i>Sleep Latency (min)</i>				
Sample size (N)	41 (100%)	28 (68.3%)	13 (31.7%)	
Mean ± SD	20.4 ± 18.8	18.8 ± 16.1	23.7 ± 24.0	
Median (P25; P75)	15.5 (6.2; 29.5)	15.1 (6.75; 22.9)	17.3 (5.7; 34.0)	0.790
Range	0.0 - 84.5	0.0 - 67.3	0.0 - 84.5	
<i>REM Latency (min)</i>				
Sample size (N)	41 (100%)	28 (68.3%)	13 (31.7%)	
Mean ± SD	121.4 ± 53.7	106.5 ± 36.8	153.6 ± 70.0	0.007
Median (P25; P75)	110.5 (85.8; 145.4)	104.8 (77.2; 128.0)	128.2 (113.7; 188)	
Range	39.0 - 333.0	39.0 - 178.0	68.3 - 333.0	
<i>AHI (Apnea-Hypopnea</i>				
<i>Index)</i>				
Sample size (N)	41 (100%)	28 (68.3%)	13 (31.7%)	
Mean ± SD	10.1 ± 10.1	6.4 ± 6.0	18.1 ± 12.5	

Median (P25; P75)	5.8 (3; 15.3)	5.2 (2.75; 7.93)	15.4 (5.6; 29.5)	0.004
Range	0.9 - 38.0	0.9 - 29.5	1.9 - 38.0	
<i>ODI (Oxygen Desaturation Index)</i>				
Sample size (N)	41 (100%)	28 (68.3%)	13 (31.7%)	
Mean ± SD	8 ± 10.6	4.0 ± 5.7	16.7 ± 13.4	
Median (P25; P75)	3.7 (0.8; 9.6)	2 (0.8; 4.1)	14.3 (4.1; 29.6)	0.002
Range	0.0 - 38.7	0.0 - 26.4	0.4 - 38.7	
<i>Snore (%)</i>				
Sample size (N)	41 (100%)	28 (68.3%)	13 (31.7%)	
Mean ± SD	23.0 ± 23.8	16.3 ± 18.3	37.4 ± 28.3	
Median (P25; P75)	14.7 (3.5; 36.1)	11.3 (2.8; 24.8)	40.8 (13.9; 63.0)	0.031
Range	0.0 - 79.9	0.0 - 79.9	0.0 - 73.8	
<i>PLMS index (Periodic Limb Movements of Sleep)</i>				
Sample size (N)	35 (100%)	25 (71.4%)	10 (28.6%)	
Mean ± SD	7.5 ± 17.2	4.5 ± 6.6	15.0 ± 30.2	
Median (P25; P75)	2.5 (0.6; 7.5)	2.0 (0.4; 5.2)	5.2 (2.5; 9.1)	0.082
Range	0.0 - 100.0	0.0 - 25.0	0.4 - 100.0	
<i>REM (%)</i>				
Sample size (N)	41 (100%)	28 (68.3%)	13 (31.7%)	

	Mean ± SD	20.7 ± 6	22.1 ± 4.5	17.8 ± 7.9	
		20.8 (17.4;			
	Median (P25; P75)	24.7)	22.9 (17.8; 25.8)	18.6 (12.2; 21.8)	0.080
	Range	2.6 - 31.9	15.2 - 29.4	2.6 - 31.9	
<i>N1 (%)</i>					
	Sample size (N)	35 (100%)	25 (71.4%)	10 (28.6%)	
	Mean ± SD	6.8 ± 4	6.2 ± 2.9	8.2 ± 5.9	0.179
	Median (P25; P75)	6.9 (4.0; 8.5)	6.9 (4.8; 8.2)	6.1 (4.3; 12.4)	
	Range	0.5 - 19.7	0.5 - 10.8	1.2 - 19.7	
<i>N2 (%)</i>					
	Sample size (N)	35 (100%)	25 (71.4%)	10 (28.6%)	
	Mean ± SD	50.2 ± 8.8	50.6 ± 7.9	49.3 ± 11.3	0.682
	Median (P25; P75)	49 (44; 54.5)	50.8 (44.3; 54.3)	46.8 (42.7; 54.0)	
	Range	35.0 - 74.5	38.0 - 69.9	35.0 - 74.5	
<i>N3 (%)</i>					
	Sample size (N)	35 (100%)	25 (71.4%)	10 (28.6%)	
	Mean ± SD	21 ± 6.9	20.7 ± 6.4	21.8 ± 8.2	0.674
		21.8 (15.6;			
	Median (P25; P75)	25.9)	21.1 (15.6; 25.3)	23.3 (18.1; 25.9)	
	Range	6.1 - 34.5	8.0 - 33.9	6.1 - 34.5	
<i>NREM (%)</i>					
	Sample size (N)	41 (100%)	28 (68.3%)	13 (31.7%)	
	Mean ± SD	79.3 ± 6	77.9 ± 4.5	82.2 ± 7.9	
	Median (P25; P75)	79.2 (75.3;	77.2 (74.2; 82.2)	81.4 (78.2; 87.8)	0.080

		82.6)			
Range		68.1 - 97.4	70.6 - 84.8	68.1 - 97.4	
<i>Arousal Index in TST</i>					
Sample size (N)		35 (100%)	25 (71.4%)	10 (28.6%)	
Mean ± SD		10.5 ± 5	10.3 ± 4.6	11.1 ± 6.1	
Median (P25; P75)		9.6 (7.1; 12.2)	9.4 (7.3; 11.4)	10.9 (6.4; 13.8)	0.927
Range		3.3 - 25.5	3.3 - 25.5	5.0 - 25.0	
<i>Average pulse in TST</i>					
<i>(bpm)</i>					
Sample size (N)		41 (100%)	28 (68.3%)	13 (31.7%)	
Mean ± SD		64.7 ± 9.7	64.1 ± 7	66.1 ± 14.1	0.544
Median (P25; P75)		63.3 (60.2; 68.8)	63.0 (60.2; 68.6)	64.4 (60.7; 71.2)	
Range		44.3 - 93.8	47.4 - 81.1	44.3 - 93.8	
<i>Max. pulse in TST (bpm)</i>					
Sample size (N)		41 (100%)	28 (68.3%)	13 (31.7%)	
Mean ± SD		93.1 ± 10	94.6 ± 9.8	89.8 ± 10.1	0.164
Median (P25; P75)		94.0 (86.0; 100.0)	96.0 (91.8; 100.5)	86.0 (84.0; 94.0)	
Range		68.0 - 110.0	68.0 - 108	77.0 - 110.0	

<i>Min. pulse in TST (bpm)</i>				
Sample size (N)	41 (100%)	28 (68.3%)	13 (31.7%)	
Mean ± SD	52.5 ± 8.2	52.0 ± 6.0	53.5 ± 11.8	0.582
Median (P25; P75)	52.0 (48.0; 55.0)	51.5 (48.0; 55.0)	52.0 (47.0; 56.0)	
Range	35.0 - 76.0	39.0 - 68.0	35.0 - 76.0	

Table 3. Sleep characterization.

Regarding the total recording time between age groups, no statistically significant difference was found, $t(39)=0.473$, $p=0.639$. The same was hold for the total sleep time, it is observed that the group of age ≥ 50 years presents lower sleep time, however, the difference is not statistically significant ($t(39)=1.245$, $p=0.220$). On average, women with age <50 years slept 24.3 min longer than older women (age ≥ 50 years).

Concerning sleep efficiency, it was lower for women in age ≥ 50 years, which corresponds to worse sleep quality in relation to young adult women, but no statistically significant difference was found ($t(39)=1.794$, $p=0.081$). The same was hold for WASO, also a sleep quality parameter, no statistically significant difference was found ($t(39)=-1.576$, $p=0.123$), even though older women present an overall higher value of WASO.

Sleep latency was not significantly affected by age ($U=172.0$, $p=0.790$). While for REM sleep latency, a statistically significant difference was found between age groups ($t(39)=-2.837$, $p=0.007$; $d=-0.95$). The effect size for this analysis was found to exceed Cohen’s (1988) convention for a large effect ($d=0.80$), with higher REM sleep latency in the older age group (≥ 50 years).

The AHI, ODI and snore (%) were all assessed. Younger women exhibit lower AHI, which is statistically significant between age groups ($U=79.5$, $p=0.004$, $r=0.45$). The same was hold for ODI ($U=69.5$, $p=0.002$, $r=0.49$) and snore ($U=104.5$, $p=0.031$, $r=0.34$).

In terms of the PLMS index, no statistically significant difference was found ($U=77.0$, $p=0.082$).

Concerning REM, N1, N2, N3 and NREM as a whole, despite the differences between age groups, no statistically significant differences were found (REM: $U=119.0$, $p=0.080$; N1: $t(33)=-1.374$, $p=0.179$; N2: $t(33)=0.413$, $p=0.682$; N3: $t(33)=-0.425$, $p=0.674$; NREM: $U=119.0$, $p=0.080$), even though older women had less REM sleep. The arousal index in TST did not present statistically significant differences between age groups ($t(33)=-0.418$, $p=0.678$).

The average pulse, the maximum pulse and the minimum pulse in TST were not statistically significant between age groups (average pulse: $t(39)=-0.612$, $p=0.544$; max. pulse: $t(39)=1.420$, $p=0.164$; min. pulse: $t(39)=-0.555$, $p=0.582$).

Table 4 shows the correlation coefficients and respective p values between age and sleep parameters.

Sleep Parameters	R	p-value	rho	p-value
TRT	-0.017	0.917	---	---
TST	-0.135	0.401	---	---
Sleep efficiency	---	---	-0.320	0.043*
WASO	---	---	0.350	0.025*
Sleep latency	---	---	0.053	0.742
REM latency	---	---	0.346	0.027*
AHI	---	---	0.289	0.067
ODI	---	---	0.344	0.028*
Snore	---	---	0.319	0.042*
PLMS index	---	---	0.193	0.266
REM (%)	-0.507	0.001**	---	---
N1 (%)	0.212	0.222	---	---
N2 (%)	0.229	0.187	---	---
N3 (%)	-0.189	0.278	---	---
NREM (%)	0.507	0.001**	---	---
Arousal index in TST	---	---	-0.085	0.629
Average pulse in TST	---	---	0.092	0.567
Max. pulse in TST	---	---	-0.292	0.064
Min. pulse in TST	---	---	0.142	0.377

Table 4. Correlations between sleep parameters and age

** *Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).*

* *Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).*

The following sleep parameters correlated positively with age in women: WASO ($\rho(41)=0.350, p=0.025$), REM latency ($\rho(41)=0.346, p=0.027$), ODI ($\rho(41)=0.344, p=0.028$), snore ($\rho(41)=0.319, p=0.042$). All of these parameters exhibited a weak positive correlation, except for NREM sleep, which showed a moderate positive correlation ($r(41)=0.507, p=0.001$).

On the other hand, the following variables correlated inversely with ageing: sleep efficiency, with a statistically weak association ($\rho(41)=-0.320, p=0.043$), and percentage of REM sleep, with a statistically moderate association ($r(41)=-0.507, p=0.001$).

No statistically meaningful correlation was found between age and the following sleep parameters: TRT, TST, sleep latency, AHI, PLMS index, N1, N2, N3, arousal index in TST, average pulse in TST, max. pulse and min. pulse in TST.

Figures 1 to 4 demonstrate correlations between sleep efficiency, WASO, REM and NREM sleep and age.

Figure 1. Scatterplot of sleep efficiency versus age.

Figure 2. Scatterplot of WASO versus age.

Figure 3. Correlation between REM sleep and age. The line represents the best fit for the correlation between them with the respective linear regression equation

Figure 4. Correlation between NREM sleep and age. The line represents the best fit for the correlation between them with the respective linear regression equation

Discussion

Several studies report ageing as being independently related to sleep fragmentation, symptoms of insomnia, derangements of circadian rhythm and modifications in sleep architecture, such as lighter sleep, decreased sleep efficiency, increased WASO and reduced REM sleep and slow wave sleep (SWS) in women. [11, 14, 15] These findings are in accordance with our results, as we demonstrated an age-related reduction in sleep efficiency and increase in WASO, although with a statistically weak association, as well as a negative correlation between REM sleep and ageing, with a statistically moderate association. We also verified an age-related increase in NREM sleep, analysing NREM as a whole and not its subdivisions.

However, when we compared women between groups (before and after 50 years old), even though older women presented a mean value of sleep efficiency that was lower than the one of the younger group, as well as a higher value of WASO, we didn't find statistically meaningful differences. Older women also had less percentage of REM sleep but, in this parameter, also no statistically significant difference was found. These results may perhaps be related to our relatively small sample size, and our cut-off of 50 years (the mean age of menopause) to compare the two groups might not have been the ideal one to establish conclusions. Furthermore, perhaps if we knew which exact phase of the menopause or the menstrual cycle each woman was when the polysomnographic studies were performed, we could determine more truthful conclusions.

When the comparison was done between groups, there was a slightly higher arousal index and sleep latency in older women and this group also presented less sleep time, but none of the results was statistically significant. Although this reduction in TST might be perceived as something negative, it is well documented that, as people get older, they progressively need less sleep time. [16]

Yet, our results showed a positive correlation between ODI and age, as well as snore and age, even though with a statistically weak association. Also, the AHI and the ODI, as well as percentage of snore, differed significantly between age groups, with small effect sizes, and with older women being more affected, and this might have eventually influenced the results.

The present study has several limitations. First, the relatively small sample size and the use of data collected from a single sleep centre may limit the generalisation of the results. Moreover, the cross-sectional nature of the study doesn't allow us to see the evolution of the same individual with ageing, but rather different individuals from different age groups. Also, as we said before, we didn't know which phase of the menopause or menstrual cycle women were in the night of the PSG recording, as well as we didn't have information on the use of caffeine, alcohol or medications that potentially affect sleep, if women used to exercise, or nap during the day, if they had regular or irregular sleep schedules or even psychological disorders, all factors that could possibly impact sleep measures. We also didn't know if women had complaints, as we didn't measure subjective sleep quality. Furthermore, a single night measure of sleep doesn't capture the variability of a woman's physiology over time and perhaps some influence of first night effect could have impacted the results.

Still, this study improves knowledge and awareness about changes in women's sleep associated with ageing, and this is particularly important since the vast majority of previous studies characterizing and diagnosing sleep disorders included mainly men. However, we need more studies that focus on the parameters where there is still inconsistency in the literature, as well as reasons and explanations behind these age-related differences in sleep, and especially why women are more affected than men, so that we can contribute to better outcomes in terms of health and well-being for the female population, and the older ones too.

In conclusion, our study demonstrated an overall poorer sleep in women with increasing age, which may be, in part, associated with a greater propensity to develop sleep disorders with ageing. Therefore, sleep complaints should not simply be dismissed as part of normal ageing. Instead, they should prompt the investigation of potential underlying health conditions.

References

1. Dorsey A, de Lecea L, Jennings KJ. Neurobiological and Hormonal Mechanisms Regulating Women's Sleep. *Front Neurosci*. 2021 Jan 14;14.
2. Haufe A, Leeners B. Sleep Disturbances Across a Woman's Lifespan: What Is the Role of Reproductive Hormones? *J Endocr Soc*. 2023 Mar 6;7(5).
3. Guidozi F. Gender differences in sleep in older men and women. *Climacteric*. 2015 Sep 3;18(5):715–21.
4. Dugral E, Ordu G. Differences in Polysomnography Parameters of Women in the Post and Transitional Phases of Menopause. *Cureus*. 2021 Dec 21.
5. Driver HS, Dijk DJ, Werth E, Biedermann K, Borbély AA. Sleep and the sleep electroencephalogram across the menstrual cycle in young healthy women. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*. 1996 Feb;81(2):728–35.
6. El Khoudary SR, Greendale G, Crawford SL, Avis NE, Brooks MM, Thurston RC, et al. The menopause transition and women's health at midlife: a progress report from the Study of Women's Health Across the Nation (SWAN). *Menopause*. 2019 Oct;26(10):1213–27.
7. Mehta N, Shafi F, Bhat A. Unique Aspects of Sleep in Women. *Mo Med*. 2015;112(6):430–4.
8. Porkka-Heiskanen T, Saaresranta T, Polo-Kantola P. Gender differences in sleep. In: Bassetti C, McNicholas W, Paunio T, Peigneux P, editors. *Sleep Medicine Textbook*. Second Edition. European Sleep Research Society; 2021.
9. Izci-Balserak B, Keenan BT, Corbitt C, Staley B, Perlis M, Pien GW. Changes in Sleep Characteristics and Breathing Parameters During Sleep in Early and Late Pregnancy. *Journal of Clinical Sleep Medicine*. 2018 Jul 15;14(07):1161–8.
10. Leach S, Olini N, Huber R. Ageing and sleep: Sleep in all stages of human development. In: Bassetti C, McNicholas W, Paunio T, Peigneux P, editors. *Sleep Medicine Textbook*. Second Edition. European Sleep Research Society; 2021.
11. Pengo MF, Won CH, Bourjeily G. Sleep in Women Across the Life Span. *Chest*. 2018 Jul;154(1):196–206.
12. Cohen J. *Statistical power analysis for the behavioral sciences*. Second Edition. Lawrence Earlbaum Associates; 1988.
13. Cohen J. A power primer. *Psychol Bull*. 1992;112(1):155–9.

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14. Moraes W, Piovezan R, Poyares D, Bittencourt LR, Santos-Silva R, Tufik S. Effects of aging on sleep structure throughout adulthood: a population-based study. *Sleep Med.* 2014 Apr;15(4):401–9.
 15. Park I, Kokudo C, Seol J, Ishihara A, Zhang S, Uchizawa A, et al. Instability of non-REM sleep in older women evaluated by sleep-stage transition and envelope analyses. *Front Aging Neurosci.* 2022 Dec 6;14.
 16. Peralta R. Associação Portuguesa de Sono. 2020. Dormir muito ou dormir bem? Available from: <https://www.apsono.com/pt/noticias/noticias-do-sono/24-noticias/noticias-do-sono/387-dormir-muito-ou-dormir-bem>.